

PIACERE

Deliverable D3.8

PIACERE IDE - v2

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Abstract:	This deliverable is the output of Task 3.5, and it will also be iterative. The deliverable will be composed of a software prototype and a technical design document. This outcome will present the IDE resulting from the integration of KR1, KR3 - KR8. A Technical Specification Report will accompany the software
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Terms and abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
CSE	Canary Sandbox Environment
DevSecOps	Development, Security and Operations
DoA	Description of Action
DOML	DevSecOps Modelling Language
DOML-E	DevSecOps Modelling Language-Extensions
FR	Functional Requirement
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IaC	Infrastructure as Code
ICG	Infrastructure Code Generator
IDE	Integrated Development Environment
IEC	Infrastructural Elements Catalogue
IEM	IaC Executor Manager
IOP	IaC Optimizer Platform
KR	Key Result
MC	Model Checker
OS	Operative System
PRC	Piacere Runtime Controller
PRP	Production Resource Provider
REQ	Requirement
TR	Technical Requirement
UC	Use Case
VT	Verification Tool
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable is the outcome of Task 3.5 which is the integration of KR1-KR7. It is an iterative task and is included within WP3. The current version of the deliverable is the v2 and contains the output of the Task 3.5 after 24 months of work. It describes the progress and improvements made in the Integrated Development Environment (IDE) since the previous deliverable D3.7 [1].

In the previous deliverable D3.7, it was described the different alternatives studied for IDE development and two options were selected: Eclipse Theia + EMF.cloud and Eclipse IDE + EMF. The IDE began to be developed with the first choice, but the lack of documentation and errors caused by the need to modify the basic IDE offered by Theia to adapt it to PIACERE's own needs caused its abandonment and a desktop IDE based on the classic version of Eclipse was developed.

The different KRs have been integrated into the IDE through APIs, in such a way that the endpoints are configured in the IDE, and it sends the requests to the different tools. For the integration, ad-hoc meetings were organized with each KR owner to carry out tests and check that everything was working properly.

The deliverable is composed of a software prototype and a technical design document. The main contribution is the development of the second version of the PIACERE IDE, this version is available in the PIACERE repository along with instructions on how to install it.

The following version v3 (latest version of IDE) will be delivered in month 30th (D3.9) together with the corresponding updated technical information. This final version will provide support for the last available DOML version and will integrate the rest of modifications of the PIACERE KR.

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1 Introduction

1.1 About this deliverable

This deliverable is the output of task 3.5 and describes the status of the Integrated Development Environment (IDE) after 24 months of work. This deliverable version adds some improvements to the deliverable D3.7 [1] and includes improvements in the IDE and updates of some modules already developed to adapt to the changes that the different KRs have introduced in this time. The next release is planned for month 30th (D3.9). In this deliverable, the final version of IDE will be presented.

The main contribution of this deliverable is updating PIACERE IDE with some new features with respect to v1. All versions, old and current, of IDE are available (for download), in the PIACERE public GitLab repository [2], along with instructions on how to install. In addition, the necessary documentation has been generated so that any user can consult it and discover all the functionalities developed to date.

1.2 Document structure

This document is structured in the following sections:

1. **Introduction:** In this section an overall description of the deliverable and its main goal is provided.
2. **Implementation.** This section describes the main updates in version 2, the functional and technical changes, and the progress status of the requirements of IDE.
3. **Delivery and usage.** This section contains the description of the current process to download the PIACERE IDE (the process has been modified by the Git repository administrator), installation instructions (open .exe file) and the link to the user manual.
4. **Conclusions.** The main works carried out during this period are summarized and the line of work to be followed for the next deliverable is proposed.
5. **References:** Where relevant additional documentation is presented as citations.
6. **Appendix 1.** DOMLizer Description.
7. **Appendix 2.** PIACERE IDE's Scenarios in Gherkin notation.

2 Implementation

2.1 Changes in v2

As already mentioned in the D2.1 deliverable [3], the central element of the PIACERE DevSecOps Framework (KR13), is the Integrated Development Environment “IDE” (KR2), by which the technical user (Software Architect, DevOps team member...) specifies the infrastructure of the application using a model-driven engineering approach. To support this activity, the PIACERE IDE integrates the DOML, the new PIACERE Modelling language used for describing the infrastructure of the application using various levels of abstraction.

In the previous deliverable (D3.7 [1]), it was described the different alternatives studied for its development and finally a desktop IDE based on the classic version of Eclipse was developed because it is a mature technology in which several project partners had a lot of successful experience developing IDEs for both R&D and industrial projects. All KRs were integrated into the IDE configuring in the PIACERE preferences the endpoints of each one.

Figure 1: PIACERE Preferences menu

There have also been changes in requirements. Specifically, the one that referred to the development of the IDE in a web environment that was related to the development in Theia (REQ GA) has been eliminated; and a new one has been added (REG 101), which refers to the creation of a graphic tool to work with the DOML.

In summary, the following sections have been updated from the previous deliverable D3.7 at various levels detailed below: section 2.2 is partially updated due to advances in the development of IDE functionalities; in section 2.3 (2.3.1. Minor changes updated to highlight the option that has finally been implemented; 2.3.2 and 2.3.3 fully updated). In Section 3 there are no changes to sections 3.1 and 3.3, but sections 3.2 and 3.4 are fully updated. Section 3.2 has been completely re-written because detailed documentation has been generated on how to use the different tools through the IDE and section 3.4 updates refer to the new repository where the versions of the IDE are hosted.

The next section will show the progress in achieving the different requirements, which have been updated during the multiple meetings that have been held during this time interval.

2.2 Functional description

The requirements for the PIACERE IDE were presented as part of deliverable D2.1 [3]. They have been collected through multiple workshops with technical partners. But, during this time, new ideas have been shared among the partners and have been reflected in a new requirement (REQ101) and also the REQ GA has been discarded because the IDE has not been developed with Eclipse Theia [4].

In this section, it is provided a summary of the PIACERE IDE requirements grouped in three tables (as in the previous deliverable D3.7 [1]), the first one contains the functional requirements, the second one contains the non- functional requirements and the last one contains the business requirements. For each requirement, an explanation of how the requirement has been addressed or planned to be addressed is provided.

Table 1: Functional requirements related with the IDE

Req ID	Description	Status	Requirement Coverage at M24
REQ28	DOML should support the modelling of containerized application deployment	Partially	The DOML supports the modelling of containerized application deployment. The current version of the IDE provides full support for DOML 1.0, 2.0 and 2.1. When new properties/elements related with containerization are required and added to the DOML, the IDE will be updated accordingly.
REQ40	The IDE should provide a visual diagram functionality to visualise the different assets defined through the DOML and DOML Extensions.	Partially	The current version of the IDE provides a tree editor to manage the DOML instances. In this version a visual editor has been added to the IDE and it will be improved in following versions. The editor let the user visualize main DOML assets, but no edition has permitted yet.
REQ41	The IDE should be extensible through the plugin mechanism. Not only to support PIACERE assets (ICG, VT) but also for third party collaborators.	Fully	The IDE is based on Eclipse and the integrations of the PIACERE some KR's has been implemented using plugins and the others have been integrated using API Rest.
REQ43	The IDE should be easily updatable to newer software versions.	Fully	The IDE is based on Eclipse, so it is easy to update, it is only necessary to modify the corresponding plugin and upload the new version to the GitLab repository.
REQ44	The IDE could provide an import mechanism to automatically fulfil partial DOML.	Not implemented	The current version of the IDE does not support this functionality. In the next iteration of the IDE will be possible importing partial IaC specifications.
REQ62	DOML must support different views.	Fully	See comments in D3.7.

REQ76	DOML should allow the user to model each of the four considered DevOps activities (Provisioning, Configuration, Deployment, Orchestration).	Partially	The DOML supports DevOps activities. The second version of the IDE provides full support for the DOML version 1.0, 2.0 and 2.1. If new properties/elements related with DevOps activities are required and added to the DOML, the IDE will be updated accordingly.
REQ99	IDE to integrate with both local and remote Git repositories.	Partially	This requirement is supported partially because public Git repositories can be used.
REQ101	IDE should allow to create and edit a graphical DOML model. Possibly starting from a palette of supported components that can be drag & drop in the graphical model	Partially	This requirement has been added to make it easier for users to interact with the DOML and is planned to be ready for the third version of the IDE.

Table 2: Non-Functional requirements related with the IDE

Req ID	Description	Status	Requirement Coverage at M24
REQ42	The IDE should be implemented using open-source software.	Fully	See comments in D3.7.

Table 3: Business requirements related to the IDE

Req ID	Description	Status	Requirement Coverage at M24
REQ64	The IDE should provide a text-based representation of DOML to ease version control.	Fully	The IDE provides a textual representation of the DOML instances created. For each of these instances a JSON file is created. The user can create as many versions of an instance as it is needed. These files are stored in the workspace of the project, but also can use a public git repository.

2.3 Technical description

This section is related with Appendix 7 of deliverable D3.7 [1], because at the beginning of the project it was planned to use Theia [4] and finally it has been decided to use Eclipse emf because of the lack of documentation and the constant problems that we have encountered when using Theia and EMF.cloud. Some of these problems are version conflict, unstable installations, problems with Theia tree generator, incompatibility with docker, conflict between different plug-ins and poor official support and documentation.

The Eclipse IDE [5] is an Eclipse Rich Client Platform (RCP) application. The core functionalities of the Eclipse IDE are provided via plug-ins(components). The PIACERE IDE functionality is based on the concept of extensions and extension points. Thanks to EMF, the IDE will support

metamodels. In the case of the PIACERE IDE, DOML and DOML-E are the supported metamodels used for modelling application infrastructures.

The IDE gives support to the PIACERE Framework. The other KRs are integrated into the IDE but not all in the same way. Some of these tools have been fully integrated into Eclipse as Eclipse plugins. On the other hand, other tools could be run in isolation and integrated through a REST API.

2.3.1 Component's description

This section is related with Appendix 7 of deliverable D3.7 [1] and lists some modelling plugins interesting in the building of PIACERE IDE. The reason why the description of the components is mentioned again is because in the previous Deliverable D3.7, Theia option was selected for IDE developing, but it was discarded, so the second option (Eclipse EMF) has finally been used and although this information is in the Appendix 7 is presented again to remark the final decision.

Figure 2: eclipse IDE components

Eclipse base

These plugins are the core of Eclipse [6] and involve the minimum plugin set to build an executable desktop application.

The current version of these plugins is 4.21.

GMF Runtime

Graphical Modelling Framework [7] is the most used library to develop graphical editors on Eclipse. It is mainly based on EMF models, and generates EMF based models too.

The current version of GMF is $\geq 1.9.0$.

Graphiti

Graphiti [8] is another library for developing graphical editors on Eclipse, that enables rapid development of state-of-the-art diagram editors for domain models

Figure 3: Graphiti Editor Example

The current version of Graphiti is 0.12.0.

Sirius

Sirius [9] is a tool based on EMF and GMF that allows to easily create graphical modelling workbenches. A modelling workbench created with Sirius is composed of a set of Eclipse editors (diagrams, tables, and trees) which allow the users to create, edit and visualize EMF models.

models.

The current version of Sirius is 6.5.1.

Acceleo

Acceleo [10] is a template-based technology to create code generators from an EMF model, that has been designed to be customizable, interoperable, and easy to kick-start.

```

generate.mtl
[comment @main /]
[file (c.fullFilePath(), false, 'UTF-8')]
package [packageName()];

import java.util.List;

public class [javaName()] {

    [for (att : Property | ownedAttribute) ]
    private [javaType()] [javaName()];

    public [javaType()] get[javaName()].toU
        return [javaName()];
    }

    public void set[javaName().toUpperFirst
        this.[javaName()] = [javaName()];
    }

    [//for]
}
[//file]
    
```

Figure 4: Acceleo template example

The current version of Acceleo is 3.7.

ATL

ATL [11] is a model transformation-oriented language that helps to convert a model defined in a Domain Specific Language (DSL) into another model defined in a distinct (or not) DSL. These include some sample ATL transformations, an ATL transformation engine, and an IDE for ATL.

Figure 5: ATL transformation Example

The current version of ATL is 4.5.0.

QVTo

QVTo [12] is another language that provides features to implement transformations between models. Eclipse QVTo is the only actively maintained QVTo implementation, and so conversely, QVT 1.2 has evolved to resolve issues uncovered by Eclipse QVTo and its users.

The current version of QVTo is 3.10.5.

UML2

Eclipse UML2 [13] is a set of plugins based on EMF that brings support to UML OMG Metamodel in Eclipse. Although UML2 provides the metamodel, it does not provide UML modelling tools itself. It is the base of other important projects like Papyrus, which incorporates these kinds of tools.

The current version of UML2 is 5.5.2.

M2E

The M2Eclipse, or M2E [14] plugin provides Apache Maven functionality into Eclipse. It allows building projects based on Maven within Eclipse, as well as integrated dependency management and other features.

The current version of M2E is 1.19.0.

Papyrus

Papyrus [15] is the most popular open-source environment for editing UML models based on EMF for Eclipse. It provides many editors such as the Class diagram editor, Activity diagram editor, State Machine diagram editor, Components diagram editor, Profile diagram editor, etc.

Figure 6: Papyrus instance example

The current version of Papyrus is 5.2.0.

EGit

EGit [16] is a set of plugins that enables to connect to GIT source code repositories.

The current version of EGit is 5.13.0.

Xtext

Xtext [17] is a framework for development of programming languages and domain-specific languages. With Xtext you define your language using a powerful grammar language. As a result, you get a full infrastructure, including parser, linker, type checker, compiler as well as editing support for Eclipse, any editor that supports the Language Server Protocol and your favourite web browser

The current version of Xtext is 2.25.0.

2.3.2 Technical specifications

The functionalities/ features added or improved in this iteration of the IDE are:

- KR extensions has been integrated, tested, and updated to the last version available.
- A Git control version has been added in the IDE.
- Supported version of the DOML 2.1 or less.
- User manual documentation has been generated. In this manual the different functionalities and their use are explained.

<https://piacere-ide-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

- A first version of requirement 101 has been developed so that users have a graphic support to facilitate the use of DOML.
- A first version of DOMLizer, a tool designed to integrate data from the PIACERE Infrastructural Elements Catalogue directly into DOML models, as well as the user interface required to access it. The full description of the tool has been added as an Appendix to this deliverable.

In addition, the different issues that partners have been reporting on GitLab have been fixed, for instance:

- Problems with the start-up.
- Support to PRC errors when the status code is not OK to let the user know it failed.
- Add DOML version when DOMLX files are created.

2.3.3 Work in progress

Currently the focus of the development of the IDE is focused on the update of the visualization/graphical representation for the different DOML elements. The following figure shows the first version of this tool.

Figure 7: POSIDONIA DOML view.

For this, the case of POSIDONIA Use Case 2 [18] has been used as an example, so that the model of the use case is represented and the concept of nesting and relationships between elements can be appreciated.

Figure 8: Detail new DOML view.

Work is still underway to specify which elements will be chosen to be shown in the diagram and how you can interact with them. At the moment, this is only a preview of the progress of this task that will be detailed in the next deliverable.

Another future task is to hide the DOMLX generation step. This point was suggested by the reviewers at the M18 meeting and will be addressed in future developments.

3 Delivery and usage

3.1 Installation instructions

See Download section.

Once the IDE is downloaded (for the corresponding OS), the user only needs to execute it to start using PIACERE IDE (for example with double clicking .exe file in Windows).

Figure 9: Contents of the ZIP file for Windows.

3.2 User Manual

The documentation to help users has been improved and this information has been placed in “readthedocs” (an open-sourced free software documentation hosting platform) [19], to make access more convenient.

<https://piacere-ide-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

The information contained in the link describes the implementation of the PIACERE IDE with a technical description and components description. A user manual with guidelines to use the tool and, finally, a link to the download site.

Figure 10: Main page of PIACERE IDE in readthedocs.

3.3 Licensing information

The license is still to be defined, but being PIACERE IDE a tool that uses Eclipse emf, PIACERE IDE license should be conditioned by the licenses permitted for products derived from this tool.

3.4 Download

The PIACERE IDE is hosted in the git repository of PIACERE under the project name “IDE”. In the repository, there is a README.md file which explains how download the tool. The IDE are available for different OS: WINDOWS, MAC, and LINUX and for different DOML versions.

The zipped Eclipse IDEs are stored in a Git Large File Storage (LFS) repo (<https://git-lfs.github.com/>) to minimize the network overload because of this direct download has been excluded. The procedure for a PIACERE IDE user for the installation is the following:

- install git-lfs on your platform
- clone the repo
- choose the IDE for your operative system
- download the selected IDE

For instance, these are the steps to download the last version for Windows:

```
install git-lfs
git config lfs.activitytimeout 120
git clone https://git.code.tecnalia.com/piacere/private/ide_tool.git
cd ide_tool
ls -l "ECLIPSE_BASED_IDE/DOML 2.1/WIN/Piacere.zip"
git lfs pull --exclude= --include "ECLIPSE_BASED_IDE/DOML
2.10/WIN/Piacere.zip"
```

```
ls -l "ECLIPSE_BASED_IDE/DOML 2.1/WIN/Piacere.zip"
```

The URL of the project is:

<https://git.code.tecnalia.com/piacere/public/the-platform/ide>

Name	Last commit	Last update
📁 Compiled Plugins	y1 commit	2 months ago
📁 ECLIPSE_BASED_IDE	y1 commit	2 months ago
📁 Source Code	y1 commit	2 months ago
📁 THEIA (DEPRECATED)	y1 commit	2 months ago
📁 docs	y1 commit	2 months ago
🔗 .gitattributes	y1 commit	2 months ago
🔗 .gitignore	y1 commit	2 months ago
📄 .lfsconfig	y1 commit	2 months ago
📄 README.md	y1 commit	2 months ago

Figure 11: Folder structure of IDE in public repo.

The folder structure is as follows: on the one hand there are the compiled plugins, the second folder is where the IDE versions for the different versions of the DOML are, and within them there are folders for each supported operating system (be careful selecting branch “y2”).

https://git.code.tecnalia.com/piacere/public/the-platform/ide/-/tree/y2/ECLIPSE_BASED_IDE

There is also a source code folder and another one named Theia (deprecated) and a folder with documentation that contains the same information that is presented in readthedocs.

To better define the functionalities and requirements of the IDE a few end user scenarios have been defined. In these scenarios the process of using the IDE will be explained using the Cucumber/Gherkin notation [20] and can be found in the Appendix 2: PIACERE IDE’s Scenarios.

4 Conclusions

This deliverable has described the second version of the PIACERE IDE, which includes DOML 2.1 version update and the first iteration of the graphical representation of the DOML. Moreover, the functionalities of the integration with other tools have been improved, such as with Infrastructural Code Generator (KR3) and Verification Tool (KR5) and new menu options for KR11 and KR12 tools. This version of the IDE is available in the PIACERE public repository and the User Manual has been uploaded to readthedocs as a living document that will evolve when new changes and functionalities are included.

In the following version of the deliverable, final version of the IDE will be presented. The new IDE will provide support for the new versions of the DOML and DOML-E, following the update schedule, and will contain extensions for improvements of other KRs into the IDE.

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5 References

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6 Appendix 1: DOMLizer Description

The DOMLizer tool provides a very simple interface to add elements from the PIACERE Infrastructural Element Catalogue (IEC) into DOML. Due to its multiple layers of abstraction, the inclusion of an external computing resource into DOML can be quite time consuming and error prone, as it implies copying lots of information from the catalogue to the DOML file. DOMLizer is a tool aimed at avoiding this problem, providing a much smoother bridge between IEC and DOML.

The DOMLizer tool provides a function to access its functionality: `addElementToDOML()`. The function can be used with 2 parameters (most common use case), stating which DOML model to integrate the IEC element into, and the ID of the selected catalogue element; or with a third parameter, defining which element in the abstract infrastructure of the current DOML is related to the added catalogue element (IOP use case).

In addition, the DOMLizer provides a menu in the IDE to access its functionality directly, as shown in the next figures. The tool detects if a DOML model is open, if that is the case, a pop-up menu appears when right-clicking on top of an element in the PIACERE Infrastructural Element Catalogue. Clicking on the menu triggers an action that call the DOMLizer under the hood, integrating the IEC element and all its related information into the current DOML.

Figure 12: DOMLizer call from catalogue.

Figure 13: DOMLizer example.

7 Appendix 2: PIACERE IDE's Scenarios

Table 4 KR3 – IDE Scenarios

Phase	Title	Scenario	Description
design-time	Open PIACERE perspective	<p>Open the PIACERE perspective</p> <p>Given An installed PIACERE IDE</p> <p>When user opens PIACERE framework</p> <p>And clicks on "Window" menu</p> <p>And selects "Perspective"</p> <p>And selects "Open Perspective"</p> <p>And selects "Other..."</p> <p>And select "Piacere"</p> <p>And clicks on "Open"</p> <p>Then PIACERE perspective is open</p>	From IDE GUI the user can open the PIACERE perspective
design-time	Creation of new PIACERE project	<p>Create a new PIACERE project</p> <p>Given An installed PIACERE IDE</p> <p>When user opens PIACERE framework</p> <p>And clicks on "File" menu</p> <p>And selects "New"</p> <p>And selects "New Piacere Project"</p> <p>And type a project name</p> <p>And select a location to save the new project</p> <p>And clicks on "Finish"</p> <p>Then a new PIACERE project is created</p>	From IDE GUI the user can create a new PIACERE project
design-time	Configure/modify PIACERE tools endpoints	<p>Configure/modify PIACERE tools endpoints</p> <p>Given An installed PIACERE IDE</p> <p>When user opens PIACERE framework</p> <p>And clicks on "Window" menu</p> <p>And selects "Preferences"</p> <p>And selects "Piacere"</p> <p>And selects any PIACERE tool</p> <p>And change "Endpoint Host"</p> <p>And change "Endpoint Port"</p> <p>And change "Protocol"</p> <p>And clicks on "Apply and Close"</p> <p>Then PIACERE endpoints configuration are modified</p>	From IDE GUI the user can configure or modify the PIACERE tools endpoints
design-time	Check PIACERE IDE version	<p>Check PIACERE framework version</p> <p>Given An installed PIACERE IDE</p> <p>When user opens PIACERE framework</p> <p>And clicks on "Help" menu</p> <p>And selects "About Piacere"</p> <p>Then version of IDE is shown</p>	From IDE GUI the user can check the version of the framework